

Electronic spectral studies and intra-molecular inter-ligand interaction in mixed ligand complexes of lanthanoids(III) involving histidine and some amino acids

Rashmi Singhai*, Vivek Tiwari and S. N. Limaye

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, India

E-mail : rashmitiwari@epatra.com Fax : 91-07582-228994

Manuscript received 25 March 2003, revised 18 July 2003, accepted 12 September 2003

The formation constants on binary ($\log K_{ML}^M$), mixed ligand complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) and stability quantifying parameters ($\Delta \log K$ and $\Delta \Delta \log K$) to examine the extra stabilization due to inter-ligand interaction in Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes involving histidine (hist) as primary ligand and α -alanine (α -ala), tryptophan (trp) or tyrosine (tyr) as secondary ligands, have been evaluated to examine the possible occurrence of intra-molecular inter-ligand interaction and the consequential changes in electronic spectral parameters viz., oscillator strength (P), Judd-Ofelt parameter (τ_λ), changes in inter-electronic repulsion (Racah) parameter (δE^k) and the nephelauxetic ratio ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$). The changes in spectral parameters have also been examined in order to observe the changes in these spectral parameters as a result of complexation and also to seek an additional spectral evidence for intra-molecular ligand-ligand interaction.

The spectral properties of lanthanoids have been studied with great interest¹ in view of their intense sharp peaks, cation solvato-dynamics, symmetry of the cation co-ordination polyhedra, f -shell behaviour and the nephelauxetic effect. In persuasion with the earlier work carried out on the mixed-ligand complexes of 3d- and 4f-block elements with amino acids² for their extrastabilisation parameters and electronic spectral studies³, we propose to examine the changes in spectral parameters as a result of intra-molecular ligand-ligand interactions.

The formation constants of the binary ($\log K_{ML}^M$) and mixed ligand complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} involving histidine (hist) as primary ligand and α -alanine (α -ala), tryptophan (trp) or tyrosine (tyr) as secondary ligands have been evaluated to examine the possibility of the occurrence of intra-molecular inter-ligand interaction. The changes in spectral parameters viz., oscillator strength (P), Judd-Ofelt parameter (τ_λ), changes in inter-electronic repulsion (Racah) parameter (δE^k) and the nephelauxetic ratio ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$) have also been evaluated in order to examine the changes in spectral parameters as a result of mixed ligand complexation and the possibility of exploring additional spectral evidence for the occurrence of intra-molecular ligand-ligand interaction.

Results and discussion

Formation constant studies :

The values of formation constants for 1: 1 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} along with the

$\Delta \log K$ values and the extrastabilization parameters $\Delta \Delta \log K$, K_1 and (%) MAL_{es} are recorded in Table 1. Less negative values of $\Delta \log K$ for larger ligands (having bulky substituted side chains viz., trp or tyr) as compared to that of α -ala (having a primitive side chain) exhibit a cooperative role played by the bulkier side chains there by extrastabilizing the mixed ligand complex. In fact the proximal ends of the elongated substituted side chains develop hydrophobicity and in an act of satisfying this hydrophobicity, a folding of the side chains may take place across the central metal. This folding may lead to the formation of closed polymeric species viz. "interacted" [MAL_{int}] and "open" forms [MAL_{op}] and there may exist an equilibrium between these interacted and un-interacted forms as MAL_(op) \leftrightarrow MAL_(int) which is expressed by the constant K_1 , (numerically equal to $10^{-\Delta \Delta \log k}$). The extent of extrastabilization have been numerically worked out in terms of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ values (Table 1B).

The magnitude of this extrastabilization, however, exhibit a sequence trp > tyr with respect to secondary ligands, where the extrastabilization with respect to metal ions found to be Pr^{III} > Nd^{III}. The sequence trp > tyr may, however, be explained on the basis of greater interaction experienced by trp than the tyr mixed ligand complexes, which is also in agreement with their hydrophobicity values⁴ (trp = -3400 cal/mol; tyr = -2300 cal/mol). Also an occurrence of aromatic ring stacking between the aromatic moieties of hist and trp or tyr may lead to this sequence. The extrastabilization sequence Pr^{III} > Nd^{III} with respect to Ln^{III} metal ions

Table 1. Formation constants of 1 : 1 binary (MA or ML) and 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand complexes (MAL) along with the $\Delta \log K$ (Part A) and the stability quantifying parameter $\Delta \Delta \log K$, the equilibrium constants (K_1 and (%) MAL_{es}) (Part B) for the polymeric exchange between the MAL(open) and the MAL (closed) forms

Metal ligand/Parameter	Pr ^{III}			Nd ^{III}		
	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$
Part A						
α -Alanine (L)	5.95	5.70	-0.25	6.20	5.90	-0.30
Histidine (A)	4.29	-	-	4.99	-	-
Tryptophan (L)	5.11	5.06	-0.05	5.51	5.31	-0.20
Tyrosine (L)	5.44	5.24	-0.20	5.54	5.20	-0.24
Part B						
Ligand	$\Delta \Delta \log K$	K_1	(%) MAL_{es}	$\Delta \Delta \log K$	K_1	(%) MAL_{es}
Tryptophan	0.20	0.58	39.9	0.10	0.25	20.5
Tyrosine	0.05	0.12	10.7	0.06	0.14	12.8

may be on account of their relative cationic sizes (ionic radius Pr^{III} = 116 pm and Nd^{III} = 115 pm) and the cation polyhedra. Both Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} exhibit an tricapped trigonal prismatic (ttp) polyhedra having a coordination number of nine.

Electronic spectral studies :

The values of oscillator strength for prominent electronic transition levels for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III}, their τ_λ values and the nephelauxetic ratio values for both binary and mixed ligand complexes at pH region of maximum complexation⁵ (pH ~6.5) are recorded in Table 2. A perusal of the spectral parameters may further extend additional evidence for the changed cation environment and the involved extrastabilisation due to intra-molecular inter-ligand interaction. The oscillator strength values for mixed ligand complexes are slightly less than their corresponding binary complexes, which may be on account of some constrains in the

mixed ligand complexes caused due to greater degree of inter electronic repulsion. The Ln^{III}-L bonds are expected to be predominantly ionic, with probable partial co-valency due to high shielding of 4f shells. Parameters τ_2 and τ_6 also show dependence on the status of metal cation. Parameter τ_4 and τ_6 which are symmetry denoting parameters expected to be large on account of large cationic size of Ln^{III} with large hydration zones. These factors are expected to cause greater perturbations in the symmetry around the coordination sphere during a vicinal Ln^{III} -L interaction thereby increasing the magnitude of these values. The increased τ_2 parameters (parameter indicative of direct Ln-L interaction) may be on account of additional inter-ligand interaction where as the increased values for τ_6 parameters may be the reflections of changes in symmetry⁶ associated with the bonding mechanism for the ligands during inter-ligand interaction.

Table 2. Oscillator strength for prominent electronic transition levels for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III}, their τ_2 and τ_6 values, the nephelauxetic ratio values for both binary and mixed ligand complexes at pH region of maximum complexation (pH ~6.5)

System	pc esu	Oscillator strength values ($\times 10^4$)				Judd-Otelt parameters				Nephelauxetic ratio	
		Pr ^{III}		Nd ^{III}		Pr ^{III}		Nd ^{III}		Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}
		³ P ₁	⁴ G _{5/2}	⁴ F _{7/2}	τ_2	τ_6	τ_2	τ_6			
Ln-aqua	0.248	5.39	15.66	18.14	1.8	4.5	1.0	1.2	-0.146	-0.21	
Ln-hist	0.383	5.88	13.32	16.89	0.9	4.5	1.1	1.1	-0.107	-0.010	
Ln- α -ala	0.399	6.19	11.29	16.52	-2.0	36.8	0.23	9.8	-0.144	-0.016	
Ln-trp	0.409	6.82	16.35	23.10	-13.5	50.1	2.37	14.1	-0.097	0.036	
Ln-tyr	0.429	6.02	15.45	16.98	-15.7	6.0	0.14	6.08	-0.006	0.004	
Ln-hist-ala	0.783	6.05	13.27	17.45	-7.8	62.7	0.87	14.3	0.013	-0.239	
Ln-hist-trp	0.809	7.65	15.51	18.08	-8.1	51.7	1.19	15.0	-0.011	-0.098	
Ln-hist-tyr	0.829	6.26	11.98	13.93	-2.06	50.3	0.54	7.8	-0.010	0.002	

The changes in the IERP-Racah parameters (δE^k) and the nephelauxetic ratio values (nfe) ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$) (Table 2) for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} (that are well within the theoretically calculated range¹⁻³) justify the validity of these calculations. The variations in these parameters for various ligand environments are indicative of the deformability of 4f-orbitals under ligand environments. Amongst nephelauxetic parameters δE^1 represent the radial elongation of the nephelauxetic cloud under the ligand effect whereas parameter δE^3 represents the orbital distortion of the electronic wave function. As a result of inter-ligand interaction the vicinity of the aromatic ring over the Ln-histidine environment for a probable stacking interaction, may influence the 4f-orbital inter-electronic repulsion. Thus the nephelauxetic parameter values are expected to depend upon $\Delta\Delta \log K$ values and or ligand characteristics. The greater +ve values for more flexible ligand (tyr) than for tryptophane (trp) indicates dependence of the nfe parameters on the inter-ligand (stacking) interaction. Similar observations may be observed for the dependence of nfe parameters and the partial charge (p.c.) (in esu) on ligand as stated here for system-pc-nfe values respectively : (Ln-hist- α -ala, -0.78, -0.239; Ln-hist-trp, -0.809, -0.098; Ln-hist-tyr, -0.829, -0.002). An increase in the nfe with total partial charge indicates towards an effective deformation of the 4f-wave function under the ligand field.

Experimental

Formation constant studies : All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique⁷ was used to determine the formation constant of the binary and mixed ligand complexes. Titration sets were prepared in double-distilled water and the ionic strength of the sets was kept constant at $\sim 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ using $\sim 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ KNO₃. Carbonate-free NaOH ($\sim 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was used in titration sets. The readings were recorded on an Orion-950 auto titrator module with a precision of ± 0.001 units. The pH titration readings were subjected to a self devised^{2,3}. Pascal compiled computer program to evaluate the formation constant values, which were then subjected to SCOGS computer⁸ program for refinement. The formation constant values thus obtained were used to evaluate the extrastabilization parameters to examine the possibility of the occurrence of intra-molecular inter-ligand interactions in the mixed ligand complexes.

Spectral studies : Nitrate salts were used to prepare standard solutions of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} in double-distilled water. The ligand concentration was maintained at $\sim 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. pH values of the solutions were maintained at two different pH values (i) the pH of mixing (~ 3.5) and (ii) pH of complexation (~ 6.5) (values only recorded). The electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 3B spectrophotometer. The values of oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt parameters were evaluated using Judd-Ofelt⁹ approach, whereas variations in inter-electronic repulsion Racah parameters (IERP Racah) for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} were evaluated using Wong equation¹⁰. Pascal compiled self-devised² computer software were used to evaluate these spectral parameters using standard equations^{2,3}.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, for facilities. One of us (R.S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. C. Gorller Walrand and K. Binnemans, 'Spectral intensities of f-f transitions', "Handbook on Physics and Chemistry of Rare Earths", eds. K. A. Gschneidner and L. Eyring, North Holland Publishing Co., 1998, Vol 25, Ch.167, pp.102-264.
2. R. Singhai, M. C. Saxena and S. N. Limaye, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 633; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1995, **107**, 523.
3. R. Singhai, M. C. Saxena and S. N. Limaye, *Spectrochem. Acta, Part A*, 1997, **53**, 353; R. Singhai, V. K. Tiwari and S. N. Limaye, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 640.
4. M. Tabata and M. Tanaka, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 203.
5. K. Bukietynska, A. Mondry and E. Osmeda, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1311, 1321.
6. S. N. Mishra, Indra Devi, C. M. Suveer Kumar and S. K. Mathews, *Rev. Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **14**, 347.
7. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
8. I. G. Sayce and V. S. Sharma, *Talanta*, 1971, **19**, 653; 1972, **20**, 831.
9. B. R. Judd, *Phys. Rev.*, 1962, **127**, 750; G. S. Ofelt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **37**, 511.
10. E. Y. Wong, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 544.